

UX and Product Lifecycle														Q = QUESTION
	Q14	Q15	Q16	Q17	Q18) Technological uncertainty	Q18) Customer Acquisition	Q18) Identifying a market niche	Q18) Game validation with the end user	Q18) Lack of professionals in the area	Q18) Lack of technical knowledge	Q18) Obtain user feedback	Q18) Organizational maturation	Q18) Financial equilibrium	P = PARTICIPANT
P1	It does not have	South America	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, Prototyping, Implementation	3	3	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	
P2	n/a	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	5	5	5	3	4	3	2	2	1	
P3	It has games in other languages, it has a multilingual team, and it has participated in international events.	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping	2	2	3	4	4	3	4	2	2	
P4	It has games in other languages and has provided services to international companies.	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	2	4	3	2	1	1	4	3	5	
P5	It has games in other languages, has a multilingual team, has a website and social media in foreign languages, has provided services to international companies, and has participated in international events.	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	1	4	5	3	1	1	1	3	4	
P6	It has games in other languages, and it has a website and social media accounts in foreign languages.	North America, Asia	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	1	1	4	1	1	3	1	3	5	
P7	It has games in other languages, it has a multilingual team, it has a website and social media in foreign languages, and it has participated in international events.	North America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Implementation	4	5	4	5	3	3	2	3	3	
P8	It has games in other languages, has a multilingual team, has a website and social media in foreign languages, has provided services to international companies, and has participated in international events.	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection, Storyboard	2	5	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	
P9	It has games in other languages, has a multilingual team, has a website and social media in foreign languages, has participated in international events, and works primarily with an international audience.	North America, Asia, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	1	4	1	1	1	5	3	
P10	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping	2	4	1	1	3	1	3	5	4	

P11	Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe, Oceania	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	2	1	3	1	2	2	3
P12	Has games in other languages	South America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Testing	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing	5	4	5	4	2	1	5	3	5
P13	Has a multilingual team	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation	3	4	1	2	5	5	4	3	4
P14	Has games in other languages	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing	Design	3	4	3	3	2	1	3	3	3
P15	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	South America, North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Feedback collection	2	4	2	3	1	2	2	2	2
P16	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Feedback collection	1	3	3	2	3	4	2	3	5
P17	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	1	2	2	4	1	1	3	1	1
P18	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	5	4	1	2	1	1	3	5
P19	Has games in other languages	South America, North America	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing	Prototyping, Testing	4	5	3	4	1	2	4	2	3
P20	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Central America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Feedback collection	3	5	3	3	5	2	3	4	5
P21	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	3	5	3	2	1	3	2	2	3

P22	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	2	1	4	2	1	2	4
P23	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	3	4
P24	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	5
P25	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	5	3	2	1	3	1	5	5
P26	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America, North America, Central America, Asia, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	3	5	2	2	3	2	3	3	5
P27	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages	North America, Europe	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	2	3	3	4	3	2	2	2	5
P28	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	North America	Testing	I don't know	2	5	1	3	1	1	1	1	3
P29	Has games in other languages	North America, Asia, Europe	Design, Prototyping, Implementation	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	4	4	4	3	1	2	3	4	4
P30	Has games in other languages	South America	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	None (does not apply UX techniques)	4	5	4	5	3	3	4	5	5
P31	Has games in other languages	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	None (does not apply UX techniques)	2	5	4	3	2	2	5	3	3
P32	Has games in other languages	North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	3	4	2	3	1	1	2	2	4
P33	Has a multilingual team		GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Feedback collection	None (does not apply UX techniques)	3	4	3	3	2	3	2	4	5
P34	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation	2	4	2	3	1	1	2	1	2

P35	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection, Ideação, Pesquisa de mercado, Pesquisas de Referencias	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	3	4	2	3	4	3	3	2	4
P36	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Feedback collection	2	2	2	5	4	3	2	3	5
P37	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	North America, Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	1	2	3	3	1	1	1	1	2
P38	Has games in other languages	South America, North America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	3	4	5	3	1	3	3	3	3
P39	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	2	4	3	3	1	1	2	4	5
P40	Has games in other languages, Has participated in international events	South America	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	4	2	3	3	2	2	4	5
P41	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	1	3	2	2	3	2	3	2	4
P42	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Feedback collection	1	4	4	1	3	2	1	3	3
P43	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Feedback collection	2	5	2	2	2	2	5	3	5
P44	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Testing	I don't know	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
P45	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	1	4	1	1	4	5	1
P46	Has games in other languages	North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Feedback collection	4	5	4	3	2	4	1	4	5

P47	Has games in other languages	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	1	3	3	3	1	1	2	3	5
P48	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	I don't know	2	5	5	5	1	1	4	4	5
P49	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events		Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	2	3	4	3	2	2	1	1
P50	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Feedback collection	5	5	4	4	2	5	3	5	5
P51	Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping	2	2	4	4	3	3	2	3	4
P52	Has a multilingual team	South America, North America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation	Design, Prototyping	3	1	3	4	2	3	5	5	3
P53	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	South America, North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, GDD (Game Design Document)	3	4	4	5	4	3	5	3	3
P54	Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Implementation, Feedback collection	1	2	2	2	3	2	4	2	3
P55	Equipe pequena, sem fundos para conseguir gerir algo internacional	South America, North America	GDD (Game Design Document), Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Testing, Feedback collection	3	5	3	4	3	4	3	2	5
P56	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	North America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Implementation, Considerando a ultima empresa eles nao consideraram em muitas etapas	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
P57	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events		Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	1	1	1	3	2	4	3	5	5
P58	Has games in other languages	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing	1	2	1	5	1	3	5	4	1
P59	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	5	3	3	2	2	3	3	5
P60	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies	North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Implementation	2	5	3	5	2	3	3	3	3

P61	I can't say	South America	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	2	4	2	2	5	4	3
P62	I can't say	South America	Prototyping, Implementation	GDD (Game Design Document)	4	4	3	4	2	2	3	1	1
P63	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America, North America	GDD (Game Design Document)	Design	1	3	2	4	1	2	1	2	3
P64	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document)	3	5	3	3	2	4	2	5	5
P65	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Prototyping, Implementation	3	4	2	2	3	2	2	5	5
P66	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Africa, Central America, Asia, Europe, Oceania	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Feedback collection	3	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1
P67	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	2	2	2	1	1	3	2	3	4
P68	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	2	2	3	5	2	3	4	4
P69	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2
P70	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	4	3	4	2	3	3	2	3
P71	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Prototyping, Implementation	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	2	5	5	3	3	2	2	2	3
P72	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team		Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	None (does not apply UX techniques)	2	2	2	4	3	3	4	5	5

P73	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	4	3	2	2	3	3	4
P74	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	3	4	3	4	5	3	3	2	5
P75	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Feedback collection	2	2	1	3	1	2	3	3	3
P76	I can't say	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	3	5	4	5	2	4	4	4	5
P77	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Africa, Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	2	2	2	3	3	4	3	5	5
P78	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	3	3	1	3	2	3	2	2
P79	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America, North America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Testing, Feedback collection	3	3	3	3	5	3	2	5	4
P80	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	4	4
P81	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Feedback collection	2	4	1	4	3	2	4	2	3
P82	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Asia, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Discovery	2	2	1	3	4	3	3	2	2
P83	Has games in other languages	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	3	5

P84	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Not apply UX	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	5	2
P85	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies	North America	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, Prototyping, Implementation	2	5	1	1	1	1	5	5	5
P86	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America, Central America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	3	3	2	1	3	4	2	1	4
P87	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America, Europe, Oceania	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	3	5	5	4	5	4	5	3	3
P88	Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing	Testing	2	2	1	4	1	1	1	4	2
P89	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	1	4	2	2	3	1	2	1	5
P90	I can't say	South America	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	4	2	2	3	3	2	4	5
P91	Has games in other languages, Has participated in international events	South America, Asia	Design, Prototyping, Implementation	Prototyping, Implementation	2	5	3	3	4	3	3	5	5
P92	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	North America, Asia, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	2	4	2	4	3	3	3	2	2
P93	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Feedback collection	3	4	1	1	1	2	3	2	5
P94	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events		Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	2	3	3	5	1	1	1	3	3
P95	Has a multilingual team, A empresa é internacional, registrada nos Estados Unidos		Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document)	2	3	2	4	2	1	2	3	2

P111	Has games in other languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Central America, Europe	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
P112	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	GDD (Game Design Document)	2	4	2	4	1	3	4	2	2	
P113	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Testing, Feedback collection	1	5	5	1	5	5	2	3	3	
P114	Has participated in international events	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	
P115	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	4	1	
P116	Has games in other languages	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Prototyping, Implementation, Feedback collection	2	5	2	4	1	1	2	4	5	
P117	Not yet		n/t	I don't know	3	5	2	3	3	4	3	3	4	
P118	Has games in other languages	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation	I don't know	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	4	3	
P119	Has games in other languages, Has website and social media in foreign languages	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping	3	3	1	4	2	1	3	4	3	
P120	Not yet	South America	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Testing	3	4	3	3	4	5	4	4	5	
P121	Has games in other languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	2	5	3	3	1	4	3	4	4	
P122	No		Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	In interface game	2	2	2	5	3	2	4	3	3	
P123	Has games in other languages, Has provided services to international companies, Has participated in international events	South America, North America, Europe	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, Prototyping, Testing, Feedback collection	3	5	3	3	1	2	2	3	5	
P124	Has games in other languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Scripting, Design, Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	2	4	2	3	3	3	4	3	5	

P125	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has provided services to international companies	South America, North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Feedback collection	1	5	5	3	5	5	3	3	3	
P126	Has games in other languages	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Design	1	2	2	3	3	5	3	2	2	
P127	It has the potential, but it's not the focus right now.	South America, África, Asia	Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing	Design, Prototyping	2	5	3	5	3	3	4	3	5	
P128	Has games in other languages, Has a multilingual team, Has website and social media in foreign languages, Has participated in international events	North America	Scripting, Design, GDD (Game Design Document), Prototyping, Implementation, Testing, Feedback collection	Prototyping, Implementation	2	5	4	4	4	1	3	3	4	